

Conference Abstract

Beyond Conventional Science Communication: reflections and experiences after a decade of “Cammini LTER” in the LTER-Italy network

Nicola Vuolo[‡], Alessandro Campanaro[§], Domenico D'Alelio^l, Emanuela Dattolo^l, Amelia De Lazzari[¶],
Valentina Grasso[‡], Alessandro Oggioni[#], Alessandra Pugnetti[¶], Michela Rogora[▫], Caterina Bergami[«]

[‡] National Research Council (CNR), Institute of Bioeconomy (IBE), Sesto Fiorentino, Italy

[§] Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Firenze, Italy

^l Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Napoli, Italy

[¶] National Research Council (CNR), Institute of Marine Science (ISMAR), Venezia, Italy

[#] National Research Council (CNR) – Institute of Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (CNR-IREA), Milano, Italy

[▫] National Research Council (CNR) – Water Research Institute (CNR-IRSA), Verbania Pallanza, Italy

[«] National Research Council (CNR), Institute of Marine Science (ISMAR), Milano, Italy

Corresponding author: Nicola Vuolo (nicola.vuolo@ibe.cnr.it)

Received: 15 Apr 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Vuolo N, Campanaro A, D'Alelio D, Dattolo E, De Lazzari A, Grasso V, Oggioni A, Pugnetti A, Rogora M, Bergami C (2025) Beyond Conventional Science Communication: reflections and experiences after a decade of “Cammini LTER” in the LTER-Italy network. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e155976.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e155976>

Abstract

Since 2015 LTER-Italy researchers have planned and realized, the informal science-communication initiative known as Cammini (Trails in Italian) LTER. Its primary aims were raising awareness of ecological issues, sharing research experiences and fostering a sense of belonging that unites those who live in a territory and those who study it (D'Alelio 2016, Bergami et al. 2018, Pugnetti 2020, L'Astorina et al. 2018). Within LTER Italy, ecosystems and biodiversity are considered values to be shared, that require collective care, involving the collaboration of all those who live in, manage, and study the area. During the 17 trails (Fig. 1), realized in 8 Cammini editions, researchers walked, cycled, and kayaked along itineraries, which connected two or more LTER sites, creating a physical and visible movement of researchers towards and with citizens, sharing informal events and communication activities, data recording, in close cooperation with the territories crossed (Bergami et al. 2018, L'Astorina et al. 2018, Pugnetti 2020). The

Cammini LTER initiative addresses the growing need for innovative approaches in doing and communicating ecological research, in response to evolving environmental and societal changes, re-evaluating the roles and responsibilities of both researchers and citizens. The complexity of these challenges calls for an integrated approach that bridges social and environmental sciences, where communication and public engagement are essential to building mutual trust. In Cammini, a combination of traditional outreach methods - such as press releases, conferences, social media, and blog posts - and experimental LTER on-site activities have been used to highlight the relevance of LTER in the territories crossed by the trail and the role of the involved institutions. Besides, more participatory and transdisciplinary practices were performed, such as citizen science, Bioblitz events, and the Sea Futuring Tours - citizen laboratories aimed at reimagining the future of the marine ecosystem, leveraging on the connections between the people and the place they live (Bergami et al. 2018, L'Astorina et al. 2018). In these contexts, communicating ecology becomes an opportunity to build strong relationships with local actors, share different perspectives, and co-create visions for the future on the territory, also inspired by the post-normal science approach (Mangia and L'Astorina 2022). Among the reflections matured from Cammini LTER, was the recognition of the need for transdisciplinary dialogue, leading to the realization of the "Cammino of Feudozzo" (L'Astorina et al. 2021), named after its location. This experience brought together researchers from various fields, to explore new ways of narrating, understanding, and interpreting the natural world. Activities included workshops, seminars, theatrical performances, and mindfulness sessions, featuring contributions from actors, epistemologists, photographers, meditation teachers, and scientists within and beyond the LTER network. CaFe provided a space to discuss various representations of nature, discuss the limitations of traditional ecological models, and explore alternative frameworks that incorporate emotional, affective, and relational elements (Barbiero 2011, Barbiero 2014, Harding 2008), fostering practices of care, able to construct or recreate intimate connections with Nature. Looking ahead, 2025 marks the 10th anniversary of the Cammini LTER. To celebrate, a special trail will be organized along the main Italian river, the Po. The journey will traverse diverse ecosystems from the mountains to the sea, using walking, cycling, and canoeing to explore the river-land-sea continuum (Fig. 2). More than 20 LTER sites, located in the Po River basins will be involved. This trail aims to highlight visible and hidden connections that link us all in the intricate web of life. The river will serve not only as a tangible entity but also as a powerful metaphor, inspiring reflections and guiding participants toward a new "era" of shared responsibility and ecological awareness. This era, which some scholars call the "Koinocene" (Favole 2021), envisions a transformative shift from the Anthropocene dominating human impact on the biosphere to a future defined by wise, participatory, and symbiotic actions that foster harmony between people, other than human beings and the planet.

Presenting author

Nicola Vuolo

Figure 1. [doi](#)

LTER-Italy *Cammini* timeline.

Figure 2. [doi](#)

A series of pictures showing different LTER-Italy *Cammini* activities. (Photos: Antonio Bergamino, Nicola Vuolo).

Presented at

ORAL

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Barbiero G (2011) Biophilia and Gaia: Two Hypotheses for an Affective Ecology. *Journal of Biourbanism* 26 (1): 1-27. [In english]. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279196444_Biophilia_and_Gaia_Two_Hypothesis_for_an_Affective_Ecology
- Barbiero G (2014) Affective Ecology for Sustainability. *Visions for sustainability* 1: 20-30. [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.7401/visions.01.03>
- Bergami C, L'Astorina A, Alessandra P (2018) I Cammini della Rete LTER-Italia. Il racconto dell'ecologia in cammino. [The LTER-Italy "Cammini". The tales of walking ecology]. CNR [In Italia]. <https://doi.org/10.32018/978888080304-1>
- D'Alelio D (2016) The Mesothalassia Bike-Tour: (Re) discovering water by riding with scientists. *Bullettin Limnology and oceanography* 25: 1-7. [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lob.10077>
- Favole A (2021) Io tempo del Koinocene. *Corriere della Sera*. URL: <https://www.pressreader.com/italy/corriere-della-sera-la-lettura/20210228/281560883521704>
- Harding S (2008) *Animate earth : science, intuition and Gaia*. White River Junction, Vt. : Chelsea Green Pub. Co. [In English]. URL: https://archive.org/details/animateearthscie0000hard_f9m5
- L'Astorina A, Bergami C, D'Alelio D, Dattolo E, Pugnetti A (2018) What is at stake for scientists when communicating ecology? Insight from the informal communication initiative "Cammini LTER". *Visions for Sustainability* 10: 19-37. [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/2804>
- L'Astorina A, Bergami C, Lazzari AD, Falchetti E (2021) Scientists moving between narratives towards an ecological vision. *Visions for Sustainability* 16 (Special Issue): 3-142. [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/5769>
- Mangia C, L'Astorina A (2022) Perché Sono Necessari Nuovi Approcci Di Indagine al Confine Tra Scienza e Politica?." *Scienza, Politica e Società: L'approccio Post-Normale in Teoria e Nelle Pratiche*. [Why are new approaches needed to investigate the border between science and politics? Science, Politics and Society: the post-normal approach in theory and practice]. CNR Edizioni [In Italian]. <https://doi.org/10.26324/SIA1.PNS1>
- Pugnetti A (2020) Voices from the water: experience, knowledge, and emotions in long-term ecological research (LTER Italy). *Advances in Oceanography and Limnology* 11 [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.4081/aiol.2020.9508>